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Analysis of European Union Maritime Casualties Crisis Management Prospective

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Abstract

According to the official reports of European maritime safety agency, 23073 maritime accidents and incidents occurred in fleets of European Union members or EU maritime administrative waters between 2011-2018.

Referring to this vast number of occurrences, 699 persons lost their lives, 7694 persons were injured, 230 ships were totally lost, and more than 566 cases of sea pollution happened. Thus, the Consequences of maritime accidents and incidents have had more economic and environmental impacts in recent years. It argued that maritime accidents could affect the ecosystem and environment of an area for a long time. That's why authorizations and international alliances have commenced to deeply study the root causes of marine accidents and incidents and then analyze them to find out how to control consequences and then look for reducing them.

This study, with a narrative review of relevant articles and library studies of annual reports of European Marine Casualty Information Platform, tries to compare data and efficient factors of maritime casualties and then recommends some policies and ingredients to reduce accidents and incidents by those factors.

Keywords: Root cause, Marine accidents, incidents, European maritime safety agency, European Marine Casualty Information Platform.

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1. Introduction

International Commercial trading is improving, and cargo transportation has increased drastically in recent years. It caused growth in maritime transition, which is the cheapest transport type. So many ships are working in their roots 24 hours per day and, causing massive traffic worldwide, moreover, increasing world habitant led to the increasing need for essential products that must be shipped from one side to another side of the world, and this substantial international trade cannot be possible without the maritime industry.

On the other hand, this workload affects the mariner's performance and needs a suitable policy to manage maritime transport with healthy rate efficiency.

Furthermore, maritime accidents and incidents have increased dramatically due to this workload; IMO and other national and international administrative organizations commenced focusing more on this field and trying to manage them by detecting the root cause (accidental events and contributing factors) of maritime accidents and incidents and trying to rectify them. EU composes EMSA and, accordingly, EMCIP to observe these occurrences and analyze them by utilizing professional and technical observation to realize methods of corrective actions. (Home - EMSA - European Maritime Safety Agency, n.d.).

Some of these maritime casualties have had long-term effects on the marine economy and environ like:

- MT.AEGEN SEA with almost 73000 MT of oil pollution in NW of Spain waters (1992).
- MT.ERIKA with nearly 31000 MT of oil pollution in the Bay of Biscay, Spain waters (1999).
- MT.PRESTIGE, with almost 77000 MT heavy fuel oil pollution in Spain waters, is named the most significant maritime pollution in history (2002).

These disasters affect those areas' ecosystems and engage the country's economy. Also, according to international regulations, territories' duties for removing pollution can have a long-term effect on the economy. The purpose of this study is to analyze data gained from approved resources and specify the root causes of these occurrences with the help of sketches and diagrams and to illustrate subcategories of affecting factors to the accidental events and contributing factors and then some ways that can be considered as a part of methods to reduce maritime incidents and accidents.

2. Methodology

As explored in EMSA annual reports, the percentage of human error as accidental events and contributing factors is 65% and more in statics analyses of maritime casualties (EMSA, 2014a). Also, after reviewing more than 15 European, American, and Asian articles with different maritime cultures, the same analysis result is obtained that approves mentioned statics figures.

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In the following items, data was collected in the narrative review method and combined with information from the EMCIP database to verify and obtain more accurate factors for further corrective actions.

- Annual reports

EMSA and EMCIP have a database and publish annual reports of casualties in European Union administrative water and flags annually. In this paper, all annual reports from the year of establishing this agency (2012) are collected till 2019 and expressed in statics methods for better underestimating.

- Lecturer review

Through research in approved and special technical journals, some well-done and relevant articles concerning maritime accidents and human erroneous and factors affecting them have been founded. This paper tried to collect data and linked them to mentioned reports from official international reports.

- Graphs and pictures

Expressed figures and percentages are shown by using graphs and pictures for better underestimating and comparing them with each other.

3. Findings

According to approved reports of EMCIP, 21395 maritime incidents and accidents in 2011-2019 happened in ships with EU member flags or in EU waters of authority (EMSA, 2014). Figure 1 shows the number of accidents, which is separated annually.

Figure 1. Total number of maritime accidents and incidents per year

These figures of incidents demonstrate that a notable observation must be made to distinguish the details of each casualty and find their essential point of view for technical analysis.

Injuries, fatalities, ship loss, and pollution is shown yearly in this era, too (EMSA, 2014b).

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Figure 2. the number of fatalities, injuries, ship lost, and marine pollution between 2013-2019.

3.1. Maritime accidents and incidents vary into two main categories.

- Accidents and incidents for ships and cargo.
- Accidents that happened to the crew.

3.2. According to data analyses by EMCIP (2011-2018), marine accidents and incidents are caused by (in order of significance):

- Loss of control.
- Collision.
- Contact.
- Damage to ship and equipment.
- Grounding and stranding.
- Fire and explosion.
- Flooding.
- Capsizing and listing.
- Hull failure.

For the total number of the accidental event between 2011-2018, 4104 occurrences were led by unanticipated events which 65.8% of them were caused by human error, and 20% were due to system/equipment failure, 9% by other agents or vessel, 3% hazardous material and less than 2% are unknown (Maritime & Agency, 2017). As contributing factor also, exact percentages exist.

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Figure 3. Swiss cheese method for the creation of maritime accidents and incidents

As stated by the Swiss cheese method, a human error is led from a ready and prepared condition consisting of 4 preconditions (Galieriková, 2019):

Organizational factors (Er & Celik, 2007):

- Inadequate education/training.
- Inadequate equipment management.
- Inadequate manning.
- Workload.
- Inappropriate operation.
- Time pressure.
- Manning is unqualified.
- Beak of safe manning level.

Unsafe supervision:

- Inadequate supervision.
- Planned inappropriate supervision.
- Failed to correct problems.
- Supervisory violations.

Precondition of unsafe acts:

- Substandard condition of operator.
- Substandard practice of operation.

Unsafe act:(Chan et al., 2016)

- Errors
 - I. Skill-based errors.
 - II. Decision errors.
 - III. Perception errors.
- Violations

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- I. Routine violations.
- II. Exceptional violations.

This study surveyed human and environmental errors by considering the total number of accidents and incidents in 2013-2019 with their root causes. By assuming human error as the leading cause of marine and maritime casualties, more than 65% of the first part is about human error and its type.

3.3. The maritime system is a people system.

People interact with technology, environment, and organizational factors. The linkage of these three parts to the personnel is essential to their performance. (Sometimes, poor links between personnel can be because of an accident, but the above linkages are more important.) (Rothblum, 2000).

Figure 4. Maritime System.

Personnel: all people who are involved in a maritime operation can be considered part of personnel for the maritime system, like the ship's crew, pilot, port crew, traffic control people, and even people who are working in administration offices, etc. And as human beings, these people have limitations and abilities which can directly affect their performance and, in the case of poor performance, can cause an incident or accident.

These abilities and limitation can illustrate below:

- Knowledge
- Skill
- Multi-task performing
- Memory
- Motivation
- Alertness
- Management

Some of these abilities can be earned by training and education; that's why the authorization department of maritime systems in a member state of EMSA should pay more attention to this part for improving the performance of personnel in the marine system by

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enhancing the quality and quantity of training. This part can be named knowledge, management, and skills.

3.4. Effect of technology on personnel

Also, now a day, in training departments utilizing simulators is one of the most common methods to analyze personnel skills and train them for more skills because using real situations is more expensive, limited, and more dangerous. Before recruiting personnel, they can be examined for their alertness and memory, multi-task performance, and management skills. Continuation of training and making relevant and suitable drills can also help personnel alertness (Rothblum, 2000).

Figure 5. interaction between technology and personnel.

Anthropometry and equipment ergonomics, alongside the layout of all tools and technical, navigational, and operational equipment, affect personnel performance directly. Also, achieved data from equipment is essential for a user or operator. This must be a manageable amount of information and less than they need; key and comprehensive data should be displayed so the operator cannot get confused and, on the other hand, could not be miss-reported with critical information. Maintenance of essential appliances and equipment is a pivotal function by a responsible person, and the senior authorized crew must do interval checks.

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3.5. Effect of environmental factors on personnel performances

Figure 6. Interaction between Environment and Personnel.

All of the environmental circumstances can affect the performance of personnel in the maritime industry, resulting in unsuitable decision-making, less risk-taking, and fatigue. Paying adequate attention to regulations, economy, lifestyle, and nutrition of personnel are the most critical factors that policymakers and employers must do precisely. Especially law and the economy can have a direct and close effect on the risk-taking of personnel. Some factors like noise and temperature or sea state are not totally under the control of industrial or company managers, but some decisions can be made to minimize them.

3.6. Effect of organizational factors on personnel performances

Figure 7. Interaction between Organization and Personnel.

As can be seen, organizational factors include all policies and regulations that regulate a working society and environment. Some factors, like work schedules or communication, can be led by a company manager or technical managers. Still, some others must be formed by practicable and accurate policies from industrial policymakers or top managers of companies, like safety culture and training policies. Then as discussed above, human error is the direct

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cause of more than 65% of accidents and incidents covered and overlapped by environmental and organizational factors. Also, organizational factors can be enumerated as human factors because managers and policymakers are human beings there. A mistake decision in designing equipment and environmental factors can be considered a human factor leading to an environmental factor in the industry (like system/equipment failure 20%, agents and other vessels 9%, and hazardous material 3%) (Na et al., 2010).

4. Conclusion and Discussion

After any occurrence and disaster, three steps for recovery of an error must proceed detection, indication, and correction (Hanzu-Pazara et al., 2008). As discussed in the last part, more than 65% (EMSA, 2014) of maritime disasters are led directly by human errors, and 29% (EMSA, 2014) of them are from equipment/system errors and other vessels taught from human erroneous indirectly.

The most common human errors are due to (Hanzu-Pazara et al., 2008):

- **Fatigue:** it can be due to personnel's inadequate rest or lack of mental capability about their duty, then can be categorized in organizational factors, and by improving suitable supervision and applying optimum work schedule can be reduced.
- **Inadequate communication:** communication skills can be earned through experience and optimum training and supervision.
- **Inadequate technical general knowledge:** it's related to the training and professional education system and must be monitored and supervised by refreshment courses and evaluations.
- **Inadequate knowledge of own ship system:** familiarity with workplace system is a significant defect in poorly structured systems and must be rectified by suitable training and familiarization methods.
- **Poor design of automation:** design of automation and information given to the operator must be optimum, profitable, and brief enough, now a day by using technology, this is rectified.
- **Decision-based on inadequate information:** information that has been given to the operator must be suitable enough for operation, not more than they need, nor less, also information bombing which is not recommended for a user.
- **Faulty standards, policies, and practice:** methods of performing operations must be supervised by authorized persons, and a systematic style must be taken into account to concern about policies and procedures of supervision on board vessels, sometimes supervision from key personnel performed in wrong ways, so poor standards settles in the company, these standards effect on maritime safety culture on society and cause methods lead accidents and incidents .these standards should be rectified and internally monitored by authorized standardized organization or companies.
- **Poor maintenance:** regular and practicable maintenance of equipment and appliances must be trained to operators, and safety culture should lead to standard maintenance.

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- Hazardous natural environment: familiarity, enough training, and using qualified personnel can reduce casualties caused due to hazardous environments.

The critical factors in reducing human errors above can be enumerated as follows (Mokhtari & Khodadadi Didani, 2013):

More surveys, more control, alert signs, accurate working standards, programming maintenance services, and increasing automation.

One of the most recommended methods for increasing personal's ability and skills and evaluating performance is using simulators (Harrald et al., 1998). In this method, self-confidence, multi-task managing skills, decision-making in a stressful situation, and standards of task operation can be evaluated in different level of difficulties and standards. Also, knowledge, alertness, memory, and motivation could be assessed in the cheapest and standard methods. Also, the detection of risks and analysis of risks severity, results, and aspects can be done by using simulators.

References

Chan, S. R., Hamid, N. A., & Mokhtar, K. (2016). A theoretical review of human error in maritime accidents. *Advanced Science Letters*, 22(9), 2109–2112. <https://doi.org/10.1166/asl.2016.7058>.

EMSA. (2014a). Annual Overview of Marine Casualties and Incidents 2014.

Er, I., & Celik, M. (2007). Identifying the potential roles of design-based failures on human errors in shipboard operations. *TransNav: International Journal on Marine Navigation and Safety of Sea Transportation*, 1(3), 339–344.

European Maritime Safety Agency. (2016). Annual Overview of Marine Casualties and Incidents.

Galieriková, A. (2019). The human factor and maritime safety. *Transportation Research Procedia*, 40(Transcom), 1319–1326. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2019.07.183>.

Hanzu-Pazara, R., Barsan, E., Arsenie, P., Chiotoroiu, L., & Raicu, G. (2008). Reducing maritime accidents caused by human factors using simulators in the training process. *Journal of Maritime Research: JMR*, 5(1), 3–18.

Harrald, J. R., Mazzuchi, T. A., Spahn, J., Van Dorp, R., Merrick, J., Shrestha, S., & Grabowski, M. (1998). Using system simulation to model the impact of human error in a maritime system. *Safety Science*, 30(1–2), 235–247. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-7535\(98\)00048-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-7535(98)00048-4).

Home - EMSA - European Maritime Safety Agency. (n.d.). Retrieved November 8, 2022, from <https://www.emsa.europa.eu/>.

Maritime, E., & Agency, S. (2013). ANNUAL.

Maritime, E., & Agency, S. (2017). Annual Overview of Marine Casualties and Incidents 2017-European Maritime Safety Agency.

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References

Chan, S. R., Hamid, N. A., & Mokhtar, K. (2016). A theoretical review of human error in maritime accidents. *Advanced Science Letters*, 22(9), 2109–2112. <https://doi.org/10.1166/asl.2016.7058>.

EMSA. (2014a). Annual Overview of Marine Casualties and Incidents 2014.

Er, I., & Celik, M. (2007). Identifying the potential roles of design-based failures on human errors in shipboard operations. *TransNav: International Journal on Marine Navigation and Safety of Sea Transportation*, 1(3), 339–344.

European Maritime Safety Agency. (2016). Annual Overview of Marine Casualties and Incidents.

Galieriková, A. (2019). The human factor and maritime safety. *Transportation Research Procedia*, 40(Transcom), 1319–1326. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2019.07.183>.

Hanzu-Pazara, R., Barsan, E., Arsenie, P., Chiotoroiu, L., & Raicu, G. (2008). Reducing maritime accidents caused by human factors using simulators in the training process. *Journal of Maritime Research: JMR*, 5(1), 3–18.

Harrald, J. R., Mazzuchi, T. A., Spahn, J., Van Dorp, R., Merrick, J., Shrestha, S., & Grabowski, M. (1998). Using system simulation to model the impact of human error in a maritime system. *Safety Science*, 30(1–2), 235–247. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-7535\(98\)00048-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-7535(98)00048-4).

Home - EMSA - European Maritime Safety Agency. (n.d.). Retrieved November 8, 2022, from <https://www.emsa.europa.eu/>.

Maritime, E., & Agency, S. (2013). ANNUAL.

Maritime, E., & Agency, S. (2017). Annual Overview of Marine Casualties and Incidents 2017-European Maritime Safety Agency.

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WWW.12MIE.IR

Mokhtari, A. H., & Khodadadi Didani, H. R. (2013). An Empirical Survey on the Role of Human Error in Marine Incidents. *TransNav, the International Journal on Marine Navigation and Safety of Sea Transportation*, 7(3), 363–367. <https://doi.org/10.12716/1001.07.03.06>.

Na, S., Kim, H.-T., Kim, H.-J., & Ha, W.-H. (2010). Human Error Analysis Technique and Its Application to Marine Accidents. *Journal of Navigation and Port Research*, 34(2), 145–152. <https://doi.org/10.5394/kinpr.2010.34.2.145>.

Rothblum, A. M. (2000). *Human Error and Marine Safety*. U.S. Coast Guard Research & Development Center, 1–9.